

Studies on the Application of 2-hydroxy-4'-sulpho diazo-naphthalene (FRA dye) used as an Adsorption Indicator in Argentometry

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2-hydroxy-4' sulpho diazonaphthalene (FRA dye) has been used as an adsorption indicator in direct or reverse titrations of silver ion with thiocyanate, chloride, bromide or iodide at pH 4-5.5. The silver compound of FRA dye has been isolated. Its behaviour and reactions provide suitable explanation for the color change in the argentometric titration carried out.

A number of dyes have been employed as an adsorption indicator in argentometry by Mehrotra and co-workers¹, Fajan *et al.*², Piazza *et al.*³, Berry *et al.*⁴, Tandon *et al.*⁵, Kolthoff *et al.*⁶, and several others. Tandon *et al.*⁷ described the use of benzene azo-1-naphthylamine as an adsorption indicator in the argentometric titrations.

In the present communication, 2-hydroxy-4'-sulpho diazonaphthalene (FRA dye) has been used as an adsorption indicator in the argentometric titration of halides and thiocyanate.

Experimental

Materials :

(i) NaCl, KBr, KI and AgNO₃ used were of A. R. grade. The stock solutions of these materials were prepared in double distilled water by direct weighing. The KSCN solution was standardised by usual method.

(ii) FRA dye was obtained from England through B. D. H. Bombay. 0.1% solution of the dye was prepared in double distilled water and kept in a stoppered container.

TABLE I -- HALIDE SOLUTION TAKEN = 50 ml, CONC. HALIDE SOLUTION = 0.001 M (HALIDE = KI, KBr, NaCl OR KSCN), CONC. Ag⁺ = 0.01 M

% Eqvt. of Ag ⁺ added	pH changes											
	I ⁻			Br ⁻			Cl ⁻			SCN ⁻		
	I	II	III	I	II	III	I	II	III	I	II	III
0	4.22	4.75	5.29	4.22	4.60	5.20	4.20	4.75	5.25	4.74	5.24	5.57
20	4.28	4.80	5.34	4.23	4.62	5.26	4.22	4.78	5.50	4.76	5.31	5.62
40	4.30	4.90	5.42	4.24	4.64	5.31	4.23	4.80	5.58	4.79	5.38	5.70
60	4.32	5.00	5.50	4.27	4.67	5.39	4.24	4.83	5.68	4.84	5.42	5.77
80	4.37	5.10	5.63	4.28	4.69	5.43	4.25	4.87	5.78	4.88	5.48	5.81
90	4.39	5.19	5.75	4.29	4.70	5.46	4.26	4.88	5.86	4.90	5.52	5.85
95	4.41	5.22	5.79	4.29	4.72	5.49	4.27	4.90	5.88	4.90	5.54	5.86
100	4.41	5.22	5.79	4.30	4.72	5.49	4.27	4.90	5.88	4.90	5.54	5.86
105	4.43	5.23	5.80	4.31	4.77	5.51	4.28	4.91	5.89	4.93	5.57	5.88
110	4.46	5.25	5.81	4.34	4.79	5.53	4.29	4.92	5.90	4.95	5.59	5.91
120	4.50	5.29	5.83	4.36	4.80	5.54	4.30	4.93	5.91	4.97	5.62	5.95
140	4.60	5.34	5.88	4.38	4.82	5.57	4.31	4.95	5.92	4.99	5.64	6.01
160	4.76	5.40	5.93	4.40	4.85	5.61	4.32	4.96	5.93	5.01	5.65	6.05

TABLE 2—FRA DYE AS ADSORPTION INDICATOR IN THE TITRATION OF HALIDE OR THIOCYANATE ION

Vol. and conc. of halide or thiocyanate	Indicator drops	Vol. and Conc. of AgNO ₃	Transition at Eqvt. point	Detailed conditions
10.0 ml of M/10 NaCl+ (1 ml of 0.01 M HNO ₃)	4	10.00–10.05 ml of M/10 AgNO ₃	Red Susp. →violet pink ppt.	Coagulation just before the end point. Color change sharp and reversible
10.0 ml of M/10 KBr+ (1 ml of 0.01 M HNO ₃)	3	9.95–10.00 ml of M/10 AgNO ₃	„	Coagulation much earlier and color change sharp and reversible
10.0 ml of M/10 KI+ (1 ml of 0.01 M HNO ₃)	2	10.00–10.05 ml of M/10 AgNO ₃	Red Susp. →light violet pink ppt.	Color change on the coagulated precipitate, sharp and reversible
10.0 ml of M/10 KSCN+ (1 ml of 0.01 M HNO ₃)	4	9.95–10.00 ml of M/10 AgNO ₃	Red Susp. →violet pink ppt.	Coagulation much earlier but color change at the equivalence point was not as sharp as in above
10.0 ml of M/50 NaCl+ (2 ml of 0.01 M HNO ₃)	4	10.05 ml of M/50 AgNO ₃	Red Susp. →violet pink ppt.	Color change on the coagulated precipitate, sharp and reversible
10.0 ml of M/50 KBr+ (ml of 0.01 M HNO ₃)	4	9.95-10.00 ml of M/50 AgNO ₃	Red Susp. →violet pink ppt.	„ „
10.0 ml of M/50 KI+ (ml of 0.01 M HNO ₃)	4	10.00–10.05 ml of M/50 AgNO ₃	Red Susp. →violet pink ppt.	„ „
10.0 ml of M/50 KSCN+ (1 ml of 0.01 M HNO ₃)	4	9.95–10.00 ml of M/50 AgNO ₃	Red Susp. →violet pink ppt.	Color change not sharp as in above
10.0 ml of M/100 NaCl+ (2-3 ml of 0.01 M HNO ₃)	4	10.05–10.00 ml of M/100 AgNO ₃	Red Susp. →Violet pink ppt.	Color change on the coagulated precipitate, sharp and reversible
10.0 ml of M/100 KBr+ (2-3 ml of 0.01 M HNO ₃)	4	10.00–10.05 ml of M/100 AgNO ₃	Red Susp. →Violet pink ppt.	„ „
10.0 ml of M/100 KI+ (2-3 ml of 0.01 M HNO ₃)	3	9.95–10.00 ml of M/100 AgNO ₃	Red Susp. →Violet pink ppt.	„ „
10.0 ml of M/100 KSCN+ (2-3 ml of 0.01 M HNO ₃)	4	10.00–10.05 ml of M/100 AgNO ₃	Red Susp. →Violet pink ppt.	Color change in suspension phase and not sharp
10.0 ml of M/200 NaCl+ (2-5 ml of 0.01 M HNO ₃)	2	10.00–10.05 ml of M/200 AgNO ₃	Red Susp. →Violet pink susp.	Equivalence point in the suspension phase, sharp and reversible
10.0 ml of M/200 KBr+ (2-5 ml of 0.01 M HNO ₃)	2	10.00–10.05 ml of M/200 AgNO ₃	Red Susp. →Violet pink susp.	„ „
10.0 ml of M/200 KI+ (2-5 ml of 0.01 M HNO ₃)	2	9.95–10.00 ml of M/200 AgNO ₃	Red Susp. →Violet pink susp.	Color change on the coagulated precipitate, sharp and reversible
10.0 ml of M/500 KI+ (3-5 ml of 0.01 M HNO ₃)	2	10.00–10.05 ml of M/500 AgNO ₃	Red Susp. →Violet pink susp.	Color change in suspension, sharp and reversible

Method :

The FRA dye shows a sharp color change from red to violet pink in the pH range 4-5.5. In this pH range halides can be titrated with silver ions with a sharp

color change of the AgX (which is also reversible) or AgSCN at the equivalence point. The violet-pink color of the suspension or precipitate of AgX (where X=Cl, Br and I) or AgSCN changes to violet on standing in sunlight for long. The sharpness in color change

during argentometric titration decreases in the order $I^- > Br^- > Cl^- > SCN^-$. The titration with silver ions could be satisfactorily carried out in the solution with dilution 0.002 M (in case of iodide), 0.005 M (in case of bromide and chloride) and 0.01 M (in case of thiocyanate).

color change occurred simultaneously and instantaneously.

In the reverse titration the coagulation occurred much earlier and the dye was adsorbed completely changing the color of the precipitate to violet pink. However, at

TABLE 3 - FRA DYE AS ADSORPTION INDICATOR IN THE TITRATION OF Ag^+ IONS WITH HALIDE OR THIOCYANATE (INDICATOR DROPS-4)

Vol. and Conc. of $AgNO_3$	Vol. and Conc. of halide or thiocyanate	Transition at the equivalence point	Detailed conditions
10.0 ml of M/10 $AgNO_3$	9.95-10.05 ml of M/10 NaCl	Violet pink ppt. → Red suspension	Coagulation much earlier and dye adsorbed on the coagulated precipitate, but at the equivalence point adsorption of the dye and red colour comes in the supernatant liquid. End point sharp and reversible.
10.0 ml of M/10 $AgNO_3$	10.00-10.05 ml of M/10 KBr	" "	
10.0 ml of M/10 $AgNO_3$	9.95-10.00 ml of M/10 KI	" "	
10.0 ml of M/10 $AgNO_3$	10.00 ml of M/10 KSCN	" "	Desorption of the dye exactly at the equivalence point, sharp & reversible.
10.0 ml of M/50 $AgNO_3$	9.95-10.00 ml of M/50 NaCl	" "	
10.0 ml of M/50 $AgNO_3$	10.00-10.05 ml of M/50 KBr	" "	
10.0 ml of M/50 $AgNO_3$	9.95-10.00 ml of M/50 KI	" "	
10.0 ml of M/50 $AgNO_3$	9.95-10.00 ml of M/50 KSCN	" "	
10.0 ml of M/100 $AgNO_3$	9.95-10.00 ml of M/100 NaCl	" "	
10.0 ml of M/100 $AgNO_3$	9.95-10.00 ml of M/100 KBr	" "	
10.0 ml of M/100 $AgNO_3$	10.00-10.05 ml of M/100 KI	" "	
10.0 ml of M/100 $AgNO_3$	9.95-10.00 ml of M/100 KSCN	" "	

pH changes during titration :

To 50 ml solution of 0.001 M halides, 10 drops of dye indicator solution was added and solution titrated against 0.01 M $AgNO_3$ solution. The initial pH was adjusted by adding 0.01 M HNO_3 or 0.01 M NaOH or NH_4OH , according to the halide ions titrated (Table 1). Every titration was repeated thrice in order to get reproducibility. The pH measurements were carried out using Philips pH-meter (PR 9405 M). The pH of the medium at equivalence point was found out by these studies.

Titration of halide or thiocyanate with $AgNO_3$ and vice versa :

10.0 ml of halide or thiocyanate solution was taken and the pH of the solution was adjusted in the range (4-5.5) by adding the required drops (1-5 ml) of 0.01 M HNO_3 . 2-4 drops of dye solution was added and the solution was titrated against standard $AgNO_3$ solution.

At the equivalence point white precipitate of AgX or $AgSCN$ acquired a violet pink color. In more dilute solution the complete coagulation of the precipitate and

the equivalence point desorption of the dye took place giving supernatant solution a red color. The observations are recorded in Tables 2 and 3.

Preparation of the silver dye compound :

About 0.30 gm of the FRA dye was dissolved in 30-40 ml of ether and 10 ml of alcohol. It was shaken with few drops (5-6) of 1 M HNO_3 acid and 5 ml of 20% $AgNO_3$ solution. The reddish orange precipitate was formed in the ethereal layer which was separated and filtered. The silver-dye compound was dried in a desiccator over porous plate for 2-3 days.

The silver-dye complex obtained is not stable in bulk, it gets hydrolysed in aqueous medium but is quite stable in ether. In aqueous medium in the presence of few drops of HNO_3 , halide and SCN^- ions give a violet pink precipitate identical to that observed during the argentometric titration of these anions using the above indicator.

The Ag-Dye derivative formed, was analysed for Ag by dissolving it in concentrated HNO_3 and precipitating Ag^+ as $AgCl$ which was filtered, dried and weighed. The results are recorded in table 4.

TABLE 4

Wt. of Ag-Dye complex (mg)	Wt. of AgCl obtained (mg)	Wt. of Ag ⁺ in the AgCl (mg)	Theoretical amount of Ag ⁺ calculated (mg)
250	73.4	55.24	55.58
350	102	76.76	77.82
450	130.6	98.30	100.05

Discussion

The color changes during argentometric titration of the halide and thiocyanate ions using FRA dye can be explained on the basis of the view of Schulek and Pungor⁸. First the particle of AgX (X=Cl, Br and I) or AgSCN probably adsorb positively charged Ag⁺ ion on its surface. The dye react with the precipitate forming a violet pink Ag-dye compound at the equivalence point. AgX or AgSCN having low solubility product is precipitated first. Just before the end point (when practically all X⁻ or SCN⁻ ion are converted in their Ag compounds) is reached, the Ag-dye complex having higher solubility product starts forming at the surface of the precipitate giving it a violet pink color. The mechanism may be expressed as follows :

The studies indicate that the pH of the medium remains almost constant near the equivalent point at pH (4 to 5.5) and the coagulation of the precipitate is instantaneous at the equivalence point.

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